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Evaluation of water/energy intensity of green hydrogen production plants in Africa scenario

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Abstract. The recent environmental concerns due to CO₂ emissions continuous growth and the contemporary increase in fossil fuel prices on international markets are two important factors that are moving the interest towards green and carbon free fuels. In this sense, green hydrogen production from electrolysis is a very promising option as a way to store electrical energy from renewable energy sources (RES) as fuel. However, two inputs are necessary: electrical energy and water. Whereas in EU scenario, electrical energy costs are the ones which affect more the feasibility, in Africa scenario, the availability of RES, in particular solar, is higher in many Countries, allowing for lower energy costs. Green hydrogen production can represent an important resource for microgrids and remote local communities, where the electrical and gas grids are not well developed. However, in this scenario, the large amount of high purity demineralized water required for the process may represent a critical aspect that must be considered. In this study, three different microgrids located in Africa (Kenya, Mali and South Africa) are analysed, considering solar PV installation, three different water intake options (ground water, surface water and seawater), and the impact of the water purification process on the whole plant from both the energy and the economic standpoints. The analysis is performed for the three scenarios, assuming the same electrolyser size (1 MW), considering PEM commercial systems and evaluating the feasibility in the three scenarios, optimizing the PV plant size (range 1-10 MW) to minimize H₂ production cost. For the chosen configurations, the water-energy-food nexus is investigated, as both the water intensity and the required area (not available for agriculture purpose) are evaluated.

1. Introduction

Africa is rich with an abundance of renewable energy sources (RES) that can help meeting the continent's demand for electricity to promote economic growth and meet global targets for CO₂ reduction [1]. This great RES potential in terms of solar and wind resources [2][3] can promote the local production of green hydrogen by means of Power-to-Hydrogen (P2H) plants [4], achieving low values of Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH) and opening opportunities for the setting up of an hydrogen economy in Africa [5][6]. The green H₂ can be employed for covering both local and export demand, with a privileged interlocutor in Europe [7] [8], also leveraging the existing natural gas pipelines as potential H₂-transport infrastructure [9].

At the same time the use of water and land (in terms for example of land occupancy by PV fields) for the production of green hydrogen poses challenges and questions in light of the Water-Energy-Food (WEF) Nexus [10][11]: a topic that is becoming more and more relevant in Africa [12] in the promotion of local energy transition [13] and exploitation of above mentioned continental RES potential [14], also considering the relevance of different water potential supply streams [15]. Considering water and land consumption for green hydrogen production [16], especially for utility-scale electrolysers [17], it is crucial to support a just [18] and sustainable [19] African Hydrogen transition, also considering the WEF Nexus [20].

Some preliminary studies have been carried out in recent years, considering different RES [21] and also evaluating food waste valorization for hydrogen production [22]: nevertheless, a detailed assessment of the potential WEF impact of green hydrogen production in different African countries is still missing. In particular, this should consider: i) local RES potential (and related land occupancy), ii) local water impact (also comparing different water sources/treatment/supply solutions and their energetic/cost performances), iii) local missed food production.

This study features: (i) three different water intake options, namely groundwater, surface water and desalinated seawater; (ii) a 1 MW-scale PEM electrolyser, fed by a nearby PV plant; (iii) the development of three scenarios, considering the impacts on the WEF capitals in terms of water and land intensity, thus its

competition with the agricultural purposes. These are evaluated to provide KPIs that could be easily scaled to assess the overall National and Continental dimension. The study has been realized in the framework of two Horizon Europe EU Funded projects, ONE-PlanET [23] and JUST-GREEN AFRH2ICA [24], which aim to study modelling tools to promote policies and strategies respectively for a WEF nexus sustainable energy transition in Africa, promoting a just green H₂ transition in Africa, in a mutual benefit cooperation with Europe.

2. Technology analysis

The technologies adopted in the case studies are here explained more in detail. As above mentioned, the case studies feature a 1-MW electrolyser receiving two inputs: electricity from PV panels and purified water after a proper treatment, depending on the water source. To better detail these technologies, a market scouting has been reported to evaluate realistic solutions, associated costs and land footprint.

2.1 Electrolysers

Electrolysis is an interesting option for carbon-free hydrogen production from renewable (*green hydrogen*) and/or nuclear (*purple hydrogen*) sources. A significant amount of electrical energy is needed to split water into hydrogen and oxygen, in the electrolytic cell, consisting of an anode and a cathode separated by an electrolyte. As for fuel cells, there are different electrolyzers' types, that can be distinguished basing on: (i) the different type of electrolyte material; (ii) the operating temperature; (iii) the ionic species it conducts. Two types are largely available today on the market: Alkaline electrolysers (AEL) and PEM electrolysers (PEMEL). Alkaline electrolysers (AEL) operate via transport of hydroxide ions (OH⁻) through the electrolyte from the cathode to the anode with hydrogen being generated on the cathode side. The electrolyte is a liquid alkaline solution of sodium (NaOH) or potassium hydroxide (KOH). Electrodes are in Nickel, without requiring noble metals. Typical working temperatures are in the range 60-80 °C, with current densities in the range 0.2-0.4 A/cm² and efficiency in the range 65-70%. They are commercially available in a wide range of capacities, from kW up to 20 MW scale and they represent a fully mature technology, with good lifetime (80.000 – 100.000 hours, more than 10 years). Hydrogen purity can reach a very good level (99.7-99.9%), without any additional purification unit. The inlet water must be very pure, with an electric conductivity lower than 5 μS/cm.

In PEM electrolysers (PEMEL), water reacts at the anode to form oxygen and positively charged hydrogen ions (protons). The electrons flow through an external circuit and the H⁺ ions selectively move across the membrane to the cathode, where they combine with electrons from the external circuit to form hydrogen gas. In this case, the electrolyte is a solid polymer membrane, which offers high proton conductivity, low mixing of the gases produced, compact system configuration and high operating pressures (up to 30-40 bar). Electrodes are in Nickel with Platinum support as catalyst, which makes them more expensive compared to AELs. Typical working temperatures are in the range 60-90 °C; they have high current densities (up to 1.6 A/cm²), and they are very compact. Efficiency is in the range 65-70%, similar to AELs. They are commercially available in a wide range of capacities, from kW up to 20 MW scale and they represent a mature technology, although lifetime is lower than AELs (60.000 hours). Hydrogen purity can reach a very good level (99.9-99.99%); on the other hand, they require higher purity water, with an electric conductivity lower than 0.5 μS/cm. The comparison is reported in Table 1 [25][26][27].

Table 1: Alkaline (AEL) and PEM electrolysers (PEMEL) comparison

Parameter	AEL	PEMEL
Electrolyte	Liquid 30% (KOH)	Solid Polymer Membrane
Temperature [°C]	60 ÷ 80	50 ÷ 90
Pressure [bar]	Up to 30	Up to 70
H ₂ purity	99.5% ÷ 99.99%	99.9% ÷ 99.9999%
Current density [A/cm ²]	0.2 ÷ 0.4	0.6 ÷ 2
Energy consumption (stack) [kWh/kg H ₂]	47-66	47 ÷ 66
Energy consumption (system) [kWh/kg H ₂]	50 ÷ 80	50 ÷ 80
System efficiency	50 ÷ 80%	50 ÷ 70%
Lifetime [hours]	90000	60000
Operational range	15 ÷ 100 %	0 ÷ 100 %
Cold start-up time [min]	<20	<5

As far as costs are concerned, CAPEX for PEMEL are slightly higher than the ones for AEL: for 1 MW size, 1600 \$/kW are assumed for PEMEL, while 1000 \$/kW are assumed for AEL. However, recent studies [26][27] show that the difference may be lower in the next years, with expected further market development for PEMEL. Considering that, in this case, the electrolyser is coupled with solar renewable energy source, which is not-programmable and can experiment several fluctuations and on-offs in a single day, a PEMEL has been considered for the analysis, thanks to its higher flexibility and the faster dynamics in case of electrical energy input variation. Input data are evaluated based on 1 MW MC-250 commercial system [28], with an electrical energy consumption of 4.5 kWh/Nm³ H₂, container area of 31 m² (46 m² with the rectifier) and dynamic capacity 10-100%.

2.2 Water Treatment (WT) units

Water supply solutions were studied targeting PEMEL electrolysers water input standards, thus targeting pure demineralized and deionized water, with very low conductivity values. Three potential water supply sources were considered:

- Seawater desalination (to be potentially exploited in different coastal areas, like in Namibia, North Africa, South Africa, the latter presented in this study)
- Ground water pumping (to be potentially exploited in favorable areas like Kenya)
- Surface water (from river and lake basins, typical of Central or Western Africa)

Table 2: Water supply technologies comparison

Parameter	Seawater desalination	Groundwater pumping and treatment	Surface water purification
Required power [kW/ MW _{ELY}]	3 kW	2.4 kW	1.6 kW
Water outlet/Water inlet (m ³ /m ³ - Water Treatment Effectiveness)	3	1.25	1.25
CAPEX [\$/MW _{ELY}]	45000	30000	20000
Footprint [m ²]	30 ÷ 100	15 ÷ 50	15 ÷ 50

3. Methodology and case studies presentation

The present study investigates the feasibility of Power-to-hydrogen (P2H) plants in three African scenarios, as reported in the previous sections, also considering the possible impact of water purification and the space that cannot be used for agricultural purpose and food production. The simplified plant layout is shown in Figure 1. The analysis is performed in three different scenarios in Africa, considering for each of these: (i) the different irradiation curves; (ii) the CAPEX for the PV panels; (iii) the available water sources; (iv) the water consumption for m² of cultivated area; (v) the amount of food (in tons) that are produced for m² of cultivated area.

Figure 1: Simplified plant layout

Solar PV energy production is influenced by solar irradiation availability, which are affected by the hour of the day and by the season. For the present analysis, the irradiation curves related to three different African Countries are considered; a local community along Bani River (Mali), a second one close to Cape Town (South Africa) and the third close to Nairobi (Kenya). The Bani River Basin, located in Mali, covers nearly 130,000 km², with seasonal water flow patterns impacting local communities. It lies in the South of Mali, in the tropical wet and dry or savannah climate zone characterized by a single rainy season. A local community in the coastal area nearby Cape Town is considered as second case study, considering purification and treatment from sea water. The last case study focuses on a local community in Kenya, not far from Nairobi, where abundance of groundwater is available.

Figure 2 shows solar irradiation values for some representative days of the year. It is worth noting the strong influence of the latitude and of the season: for Bani River and for Nairobi, the latitudes are +11° N and 1°S respectively, with significantly higher average irradiation compared to Cape Town (33°S). It is worth noting that the difference in absolute terms between the different months are limited for latitude close to the Equator, while the influence increases for South Africa scenario. According to GIS and to recent literature, the solar potential in terms of global horizontal irradiation is 6.08 kWh/m²/day in Mali [29][30], 5.1 kWh/m²/day in South Africa [31][32] and 6.2 kWh/m²/day in Kenya [33][34] scenarios.

The electrical energy production from the installed PV panels is calculated as follows:

$$Prod. el. energy PV [kWh] = \frac{Irradiance \left[\frac{Wh}{m^2} \right] \cdot PV Area [m^2] \cdot \eta}{1000} \quad (1)$$

Where the average efficiency η is assumed 16%, the irradiance is a time-dependent parameter, according to the scenario (as reported in Figure 2), and the PV area, which is directly connected to the installed power (6 m² are needed for 1 kW power), is an input variable for the model. After calculating the energy production, it is worth determining the equivalent hours as well, both for the PV and for the PEM electrolyser, considering that a limited amount of electricity is needed for the Water Treatment section and that the maximum power which can be used by the PEMEL is 1 MW. The PEMEL equivalent hours are calculated comparing the hydrogen effective production in one year and the hydrogen hourly maximum production:

$$PV \text{ equivalent hours } [h] = \frac{prod. el. energy [kWh]}{Installed power [kW]} \quad (2)$$

$$PEMEL \text{ equivalent hours } [h] = \frac{H_2 \text{ produced } [kgH_2]}{\frac{installed power [kW]}{el. en. consumption \left[\frac{kWh}{kgH_2} \right]}} \quad (3)$$

For hydrogen production calculation, the assumptions reported in section 2.1 are employed.

Figure 2: Average monthly irradiation profiles for the Mali (up), South Africa (centre) and Kenya (below)

The economic analysis is performed considering the costs related to investment and management of the PV plant (whose size is variable from 1 up to 10 MW), of the PEMEL (fixed size 1 MW) and of the WT plant, sized to produce 0.2 m³/h pure water for the 1 MW PEMEL. The CAPEX for the water treatment depends on the water source and on the size, according to Eq. (1), as follows:

$$C = C_0 \cdot \left(\frac{S}{S_0}\right)^{0.65} \quad (4)$$

Where the cost C_0 for a fixed size S_0 (corresponding to 2 m³/h of purified water, equivalent to 10 MW electrolyser) are available from recent case studies in case of seawater (450,000 \$), river/lake water (300,000 \$) and ground water (200,000 \$). For 1 MW PEMEL, it is easy to calculate the corresponding WT investment, for the different water sources. As far as the PEMEL is concerned, costs are extrapolated by recent literature [25][26][27], considering a stack replacement after 8 years for conservative reasons [25]. The PV plant has the main purpose to support the green hydrogen, however, mainly in summer periods, electrical energy not employed by the P2H plant can be employed for other purposes by local users: thus, a valorization of this electrical energy can be considered. Three scenarios are investigated:

- Off-grid scenario (the exceeding electrical energy is not sold)
- On-grid scenario A (the exceeding electrical energy is sold at 0.02 \$/kWh)
- On-grid scenario B (the exceeding electrical energy is sold at 0.04 \$/kWh)

The main input data for economic analysis are reported in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Main input data for economic analysis

Parameter	Value	Ref
PEM electrolyser CAPEX [\$/kW]	1600	[25][26][27]
PEM electrolyser OPEX	2% CAPEX/year	[25]
PEM extra CAPEX	50% CAPEX (after 8 years)	[25]
PV CAPEX [\$/kW]	1250	[36]
PV OPEX	1% CAPEX/year	[36]
Water Treatment CAPEX	Eq. (1)	
Water Treatment OPEX	2% CAPEX/year	
Plant lifetime [years]	20	
El. Energy selling price [\$/kWh]	0 – 0.02 – 0.04	

Plant analysis is performed on a complete year time period, considering a representative average day for each month to take into account the time dependent nature of the solar energy. The first aim of the study is the techno-economic analysis on the whole system, determining the best size of the PV to minimize levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) production, defined as follows:

$$LCOH \left[\frac{\$}{kg} \right] = \frac{CAPEX_{tot} + \sum_{i=1}^N (OPEX_{tot})_i + (CAPEX)_{extra} - Revenues}{\sum_{i=1}^N (H_2 \text{ produced})_i} \quad (5)$$

4. Main results and discussion

In this section, the results are presented for each scenario: considering the different solar availability curves (reported in Figure 2), and the different water sources (river water for Mali, seawater for South Africa and ground water for Kenya), the CAPEX distribution and the LCOH are determined for different PV installed sizes. The minimum LCOH is determined, considering different assumptions for the exceeding electrical energy from PV (not employed for green H₂ production): in the most conservative case, this energy is not valorised, in the other cases it can be sold to nearby users at two different prices. Once the minimum LCOH is determined, the PEMEL capacity factor in the different months of the year is calculated for the best PV size configuration.

4.1 Bani River Basin (Mali)

Figure 3 shows the trend for the Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen (LCOH) for different PV sizes, in the range 1 – 10 MW, considering 1 MW fixed size for PEMEL and a corresponding WT unit to have 0.2 Nm³/h (200 l/h) of demineralized water. In the most conservative case, represented by a system not connected to the National grid (off-grid scenario), the lowest LCOH of 5.3 \$/kg is obtained for 1.8 MW of PV panels (nearly 10800 m² area); increasing the PV panels installed power would lead to higher hydrogen production, but also to higher costs. In the on-grid scenarios A (electrical energy sold at nearby users at 0.02 \$/kWh) and B (electrical energy sold at nearby users at 0.04 \$/kWh), costs would be obviously reduced.

By analyzing the CAPEX distribution for the optimal size, reported in Figure 4, it can be observed that the most important impact is given by the PV modules, which explains why larger PV sizes would negatively affect the result, in case of no electrical energy selling to external users; however, even in case of electricity valorization at 0.02 \$/kWh, the trend would remain similar. It is also interesting to observe that the impact of WT is limited.

Figure 3: LCOH for different PV size, Mali scenario

Figure 4: CAPEX distribution for 1.8 MW PV size (Mali)

Table 4 summarizes the energy results related to both PV and PEMEL productions. With the chosen configuration (1.8 MW PV), the most of electricity produced by PV is employed for H₂ production (79%), with an extra production for other nearby electricity users only in a few months. The capacity factor of the PEMEL is not strongly affected by the month (minimum 32%, maximum 38%), as can be expected, since the PV production is quite constant due also to the favourable scenario.

Table 4: Main energy results for green H₂ production (Mali)

	H ₂ produced [kg]	PEMEL Capacity factor	El en. Produced by PV [MWh]	El. en to other users [MWh]
Jan	5613	38.2%	400.01	115.65
Feb	5082	38.3%	366.22	108.71
Mar	5513	37.5%	374.15	94.81
Apr	5132	36.1%	322.03	61.97
May	4985	33.9%	279.98	27.35
Jun	4608	32.4%	248.96	15.41
Jul	4705	32.0%	245.31	6.83
Aug	4758	32.4%	250.39	9.21
Sep	5024	35.3%	295.18	40.61
Oct	5414	36.8%	361.89	87.54
Nov	5395	37.9%	388.88	115.58
Dec	5645	38.4%	410.70	124.69
Annual	61873	35.7%	3943.72	808.37

Figure 5 shows the influence of the PV installed size on the energy and economic results, represented by the equivalent operating hours and the Total Capital Investment (TCI), respectively. The solar operating hours are slightly higher than 2000, representing a good value thanks to the favourable scenario: as it can be expected, this value is not influenced by the PV size; on the other hand, increasing the PV dimensions, and keeping the same PEMEL 1 MW size, the equivalent hours for the PEMEL increase; however, the increase is not linear: for 1 MW the EOH are 2200, for 1.8 MW they are 3130, for 6 MW 3810, for 10 MW 3920. At the same time, the CAPEX grows significantly, as the PV is the most expensive component: thus, it is not convenient to have an excessive PV solar dimensions, and the best LCOH, as shown also in Figure 3, is obtained for 1.8 MW PV solar.

Figure 5: Influence of PV size on Equivalent operating hours and TCI (Mali)

4.2 South Africa

In this second case, the considered scenario is the city of Cape Town in South Africa and the demi water for the PEM electrolyser is obtained from sea water, with a proper WT system. Although in this case, the cost is slightly higher, its impact in terms of CAPEX and energy consumption is still very limited (3% of CAPEX, less than 1% of the total electrical energy input).

Figure 6 shows the trend for the Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen (LCOH) for different PV sizes, in the range 1 – 10 MW, considering 1 MW fixed size for PEMEL and a corresponding WT unit to have 0.2 Nm³/h (200 l/h) of demineralized water. In this case, in the most conservative case, represented by a system not connected to the National grid, the lowest LCOH results 5.9 \$/kg, in this case obtained for 2 MW of PV panels (nearly 12000 m² area); increasing the PV panels installed power would lead to higher hydrogen production, but also to higher costs.

Table 5 summarizes the energy results related to both PV and PEMEL productions. With the chosen configuration (2 MW PV), the most of electricity produced by PV is employed for H₂ production (90%), with an extra production for other nearby electricity users only in a few months. In this case, it is worth noting that the capacity factor of the PEMEL is strongly affected by the month, since the PV production is not constant and significantly influenced by the period of the year, ranging from low values from May to September, with no extra power for other users, up to the highest capacity factors in December and in January (nearly 50%). However, the global value throughout the year results slightly lower than in previous scenario (34% vs 35%), although the PV size is higher (2 MW vs 1.8 MW).

Figure 6: LCOH for different PV size, South Africa scenario

Table 5: Main energy results for green H₂ production (Cape Town, South Africa)

	H ₂ produced [kg]	PEMEL capacity factor	El. en. Produced by PV [MWh]	El. en to other users [MWh]
Jan	7313	49.7%	513.05	142.01
Feb	6197	46.6%	404.34	89.94
Mar	5856	39.8%	331.72	34.44
Apr	4466	31.4%	233.69	6.92
May	2922	19.9%	148.64	0
Jun	2623	18.4%	133.49	0
Jul	2621	17.8%	133.44	0
Aug	2742	18.6%	133.62	0
Sep	4407	31.0%	223.92	0.04
Oct	5843	39.7%	322.15	25.47
Nov	6733	47.3%	408.90	67.23
Dec	7486	50.9%	487.70	107.93
Annual	59211	34.2%	3480.65	473.98

4.3 Kenya

In the third case, the considered scenario is located in Kenya, at a latitude very close to the Equator. In this case, the demi water for the PEM electrolyser is obtained from ground water, with a proper WT system. Also in this case, the WT impact in terms of CAPEX and energy consumption is very limited (2% of CAPEX, less than 1% of the total electrical energy input).

Figure 7 shows the trend for the LCOH for different PV sizes, in the range 1 – 10 MW, considering 1 MW fixed size for PEMEL and a corresponding WT unit to have 0.2 Nm³/h (200 l/h) of demineralized water. In the most conservative case, represented by a system not connected to the National grid, the lowest LCOH results 4.8 \$/kg, in this case obtained for 1.8 MW of PV panels (nearly 10800 m² area); increasing the PV panels installed power would lead to higher hydrogen production, but also to higher costs.

Figure 7: LCOH for different PV size, Kenya scenario

Table 6 summarizes the energy results related to both PV and PEMEL productions. With the chosen configuration (1.8 MW PV), the most of electricity produced by PV is employed for H₂ production (85%), with an extra production for other nearby electricity users only in a few months. As in the first scenario, it is worth noting that the capacity factor of the PEMEL is not strongly affected by the period of the year, since the PV production is quite constant due to a similar daylight hours in the different seasons; the minimum values are in June and July, with very low extra power for other users, and PEMEL capacity factor of nearly 36%, while the maximum value is nearly constant from December up to March, with values of about 40%. The average capacity factor for PEMEL throughout the year results higher than in the other scenarios (39%).

Table 6: Main energy results for green H₂ production (Kenya)

	H ₂ produced [kg]	PEMEL capacity factor	El en. Produced by PV [MWh]	El. en to other users [MWh]
Jan	6042	41.1%	375.91	69.98
Feb	5491	41.3%	387.21	109.22
Mar	6277	42.7%	421.24	103.45
Apr	5795	40.7%	358.42	64.99
May	5659	38.5%	324.15	37.61
Jun	5092	35.8%	265.80	7.93
Jul	5350	36.4%	283.81	12.88
Aug	5461	37.1%	299.48	22.96
Sep	5525	38.8%	329.05	49.31
Oct	6050	41.1%	363.34	57.05
Nov	5463	38.4%	325.31	48.70
Dec	5988	40.7%	376.42	73.22
Annual	68193	39,4%	4110.14	657.31

5. Water-Energy-Food Nexus impact assessment

In order to evaluate the WEF Nexus impact of the three green hydrogen case studies, the main agricultural cultivation of the Countries have been analysed, evaluating the local annual production and the main land and water use statistics [36] [37], as reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Agricultural references for the three use cases countries

	South Africa	Kenya	Mali
Total country surface [ha]	$1.4 \cdot 10^8$	$5.8 \cdot 10^7$	$1.24 \cdot 10^8$
Land used for agricultural purposes [ha]	$1.4 \cdot 10^7$	$0.64 \cdot 10^7$	$0.85 \cdot 10^7$
Annual water consumption for agriculture [m^3/yr]	$1.2 \cdot 10^{10}$	$0.32 \cdot 10^{10}$	$0.51 \cdot 10^{10}$
Specific yearly water consumption [m^3/m^2]	0,097	0,050	0,060
Main agricultural cultivation	Corn	Corn	Millet
Land dedicated to main agricultural cultivation [ha]	$2.76 \cdot 10^6$	$2.16 \cdot 10^6$	$1.49 \cdot 10^6$
Annual production [t]	$1.62 \cdot 10^7$	$0.41 \cdot 10^7$	$0.11 \cdot 10^7$
Agricultural production [t/ha per year]	5.88	1.89	0.77

Considering previous chapter estimations of PV surface needed to provide RES power to 1 MW_{el} PEM electrolyser as well as footprint of electrolysis and water treatment and purification systems, it is possible to calculate, according to reference values reported in Table 7, some KPIs related to the WEF Nexus impact that a 1 MW green hydrogen production plant could have on local land occupancy, missed food production and water not used for agricultural purposes (thus “stolen” to food production) as reported in Table 8.

Table 8: WEF Nexus Impact of a 1 MW PEM Ely electrolyser

	South Africa	Kenya	Mali
Overall land occupancy of the green H ₂ plant [ha]	1.2	1.09	1.08
Water consumption of the green H ₂ plant [m^3]	1040	571	548
Specific Yearly Water consumption [m^3/m^2]	0.087	0.053	0.051
Missed food production according to green H ₂ plant land occupancy [t/yr]	7.08	2.05	0.84
Missed irrigated land due to water use for green H ₂ production [ha]	1.08	1.13	0.92

Observing Table 7 and Table 8 values, it is worth to highlight that the WEF nexus impact of a green hydrogen production plant is not really significant as some KPIs (for example of water and land consumption) are very similar each other in the two tables (with higher values in table 7) and missed food production (on the overall national production of the countries) look negligible even foreseeing hundreds of MW of electrolysis plant installations. It is worthy to highlight that, the promotion of green hydrogen plants, could also have a beneficial purpose at local level: 1) stimulating the setup of water desalination or purification plants that can provide water also to local irrigation/agricultural purposes, 2) stimulating the setup of RES power plants also facilitating electrification of local rural/agricultural areas.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, the authors investigated green H₂ production for three different case studies in Africa, evaluating the energy and economic feasibility and also considering the Water-Energy-Food nexus. The impact of the water treatment plant on hydrogen production was evaluated considering three different water sources, namely ground water, river and seawater, and evaluating the impact in terms of both energy intensity and costs to obtain demi water for feeding 1 MW PEM electrolyser. Then, the optimal installed PV size was determined in order to minimize the LCOH in each scenario (local community in Mali, South Africa and Kenya). At the end, for the optimal sizes, the water intensity and the ground occupation were determined, thus defining the total area which cannot be dedicated to food production by agriculture in the three scenarios. The results allow for the following conclusions to be drawn:

- The water treatment plant, even in the worst case (South Africa, seawater) has a limited contribute both in terms of energy consumption (less than 1% on annual basis) and of CAPEX (3% of the total, very low if compared to PEMEL and PV panels), thus not affecting significantly the LCOH;
- Thanks to the good solar potential and the constant solar production in the different months of the year, in Kenya and Mali scenarios, it is possible to obtain promising LCOH (4.8 and 5.3 \$/kg, respectively), with optimal PV sizes of 1.8 MW and production of 62 and 68 ton/year of green H₂; in

the South Africa case, the LCOH is about 5.9 \$/kg, with optimal PV size of 2 MW and lower capacity factor for the PEMEL;

- In all the considered scenarios, the results are calculated not considering surplus electricity selling to local users, as off-grid scenarios are assumed, with no direct connection with the National grid;
- For the three scenarios, the water consumption per m² for hydrogen production is compared with water intensity for agriculture use, finding out that the water intensity is very similar: thus, the solution results sustainable from the water intensity standpoint;
- For the three scenarios, the total area for Power-to-hydrogen plants are due mostly to PV panels: in each case, the equivalent food which cannot be produced due to land occupation are evaluated, finding out limited annual values for all the three scenarios.

In conclusion, the results are encouraging from both the economic and the WEF Nexus standpoints: future work will include different applications in the African continent, also considering the possibility of electricity selling to nearby local users, and/or co-produced Oxygen valorization to improve the economic performance.

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